

Full Research Paper

Designing with Callon's theory of translation to realise deep stakeholder engagement towards co-creating system level change in Living Labs: the case of ReNu2Cycle

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Abstract

Role-play simulations are increasingly recognised as valuable tools for experiential learning, stakeholder dialogue, and collaborative problem-solving in complex innovation ecosystems. This paper introduces the *Process of Translation Serious Game*, designed to explore negotiation and alignment within Living Lab contexts. Grounded in Michel Callon's theory of translation and the concept of Obligatory Passage Points, the game creates a structured setting where participants embody actors from across the quadruple helix, academia, industry, government, and civil society. Through role-play, participants engage with the diverse interests and constraints that shape co-creation, simulating how alignment is negotiated in real-world innovation processes. The game was piloted at the European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative (ESNI) 2024 conference with researchers and policymakers. Drawing on observational data, the paper examines how participants inhabited their roles, navigated conflict, and worked toward consensus. Findings show that the game helps surface hidden assumptions, foster empathy, and support critical reflection on power, legitimacy, and collaboration. We argue that serious play can enrich Living Lab practice by offering a dynamic method for engaging with stakeholder complexity and building capacity for mission-oriented innovation. The paper concludes with recommendations for integrating role-play simulations into Living Lab methodologies to support deeper and more inclusive stakeholder engagement.

Key words

Living Labs, Translation, Callon, Serious Game

Introduction

Living Labs have emerged as key sites of mission-oriented innovation and place-based experimentation (Dvarioniene, et al 2015; Engels et al., 2019). Operating as user-centered, real-life environments, they bring together actors from academia, industry, government, and civil society to co-develop and test solutions to pressing societal challenges. In these multi-actor contexts, effective stakeholder engagement is both a critical success factor and an enduring challenge. Power asymmetries, divergent interests, and limited capacity for deep collaboration frequently inhibit meaningful co-creation (Hansen & Fuglsang, 2020). To address these challenges, various participatory methods have been deployed, ranging from workshops and co-design sessions to digital simulations (Huang & Thomas, 2021; Mbatha & Musango, 2022). While valuable, these methods often fall short in simulating the lived experience of negotiation, trade-offs, and alignment that underpin innovation in complex systems. Existing approaches tend to either flatten conflict or rely heavily on linear consultation, limiting their capacity to reveal how consensus is built, or resisted, within multi-stakeholder networks.

This paper introduces the Process of Translation Serious Game (PoTSG), a role-play simulation developed to surface the performative, relational, and emotional dimensions of stakeholder alignment in Living Labs. The game was piloted with researchers and policymakers at the European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative (ESNI) 2024 conference and is designed to help participants embody the roles of diverse actors working toward a shared matter of concern. Unlike many serious games that focus on decision-making or system dynamics, PoTSG centers on the *work of translation*, the often-invisible processes through which actors negotiate interests, reframe problems, and build alliances. The game's design is inspired by Michel Callon's concept of *translation* and particularly his notion of Obligatory Passage Points (OPPs), critical junctures through which actors must align to move forward. However, rather than presenting this theory in abstract terms, the game uses it to structure an embodied experience, helping participants feel what it means to compromise, to assert legitimacy, or to find one's position marginal within a system of power.

In doing so, PoTSG fills a notable gap in Living Lab methodology. It offers a pedagogical and research tool that can be used to support stakeholder reflexivity, empathy, and collaborative problem-framing. Importantly, it does not seek to replace existing methods but to complement them, offering a way to simulate and reflect on the very dynamics that other tools often assume. In what follows, we explain the theoretical foundations of the

game, outline its structure and pilot implementation, and discuss the insights gained about the conditions for effective stakeholder alignment.

Introducing the PoT Serious Game

The Theory of Translation Serious Game, titled “*Building the Common Ground*”, is a role-play-based intervention designed to facilitate stakeholder collaboration in sustainability and circular economy contexts, particularly within agricultural systems. Developed by the authors, the game draws explicitly on Michel Callon’s theory of translation (Callon, 1986), focusing on the process of identifying and negotiating Obligatory Passage Points (OPPs), those critical points through which diverse actors must pass to achieve alignment. The game was designed and developed by the authors as part of the Interreg NW funded ReNu2Cycle project. The overall objective is to reduce NWE’s dependency on fossil-based fertiliser imports with proven impacts on availability, ecological footprint and price stability via transregional valorisation of recycled NPK from municipal, industrial waste and agricultural sector in Flanders, The Netherlands, Ireland, Saarland, Lower Saxony, Luxembourg.

Game Structure and Objectives

Participants embody one of several roles representing actors from the quadruple helix: academia, industry, government, and civil society. Each actor enters with their own goals, constraints, and interests. Through a series of structured phases, including introductions, negotiation, synergy building, and consensus drafting, players work towards articulating a shared *matter of concern*. The core aim is to simulate the relational, political, and discursive work required to align heterogeneous actors around a common goal, echoing Callon’s problematisation stage in actor-network theory.

Key features of the game include:

- **Role play:** Participants stay “in character” to faithfully enact the interests and constraints of their assigned actor.
- **Facilitated negotiation:** Discussions are moderated to ensure constructive debate and to surface tensions and synergies between positions.
- **Reflection on process:** Players are encouraged to reflect on compromises made and the dynamics of reaching consensus.

The objective of the game was shared with participants as “All actors must work together to find a shared matter of concern that everyone in the network can agree upon, related

to sustainability, circular economy, and agricultural practices. This could be a shared goal, policy, or action plan”. Each player is asked to choose one card, where their name, organisation and reason for engaging in the living lab was presented. The player studies the card and then each introduce themselves according to the details on the card, and where they could elaborate based on their own knowledge but maintaining the integrity of the role being played. The following were offered as the “rules of the game”: Time Limits: Each phase has a time limit to keep the game moving. No Absolute Wins: The goal is not for one actor to “win” but for all actors to leave satisfied with a shared plan. Compromise Incentives: If a player refuses to compromise, the facilitator or another player can invoke real-world challenges (e.g., new environmental regulations) that require them to adjust their position. Role Sticking: Players must stay in character throughout the game, arguing from their actor’s perspective even if it challenges their own real-world views.

Conceptual Framing: From Participation to Translation

The literature on stakeholder engagement in Living Labs increasingly calls for approaches that go beyond participation to foster deeper forms of mutual understanding and alignment (Malakhatka et al., 2024). A particular gap in the literature concerns methods that allow stakeholders to “step into the shoes” of others, gaining experiential insights into the perspectives, constraints, and motivations of different actors in the innovation system. While participatory design methods foster collaboration, they often fall short of simulating the affective and cognitive experiences of negotiation, compromise, and alignment that shape real-life innovation processes (Hansen & Fuglsang, 2020). Role-play simulations (RPS) and serious games, widely used in education and policy negotiation contexts, offer a promising yet underexplored avenue for addressing this gap in Living Lab practice (Scerri & Attard, 2023; Mandic et al., 2024).

As scholars have noted, co-creation is rarely a smooth or neutral process and involves navigating power asymmetries, epistemic differences, and institutional constraints. This demands methods that help actors reflect on their roles, confront tensions, and negotiate shared goals. Michel Callon’s sociology of translation, developed within Science and Technology Studies (STS), offers a helpful lens here. Rather than viewing knowledge as something to be transmitted from experts to users, Callon highlights how knowledge, interests, and roles are co-produced through interaction. Translation, in this view, is the process by which actors make themselves—and their ideas—meaningful to others. It is inherently relational and political. This framing is particularly useful in Living Lab contexts, where the roles of “expert” and “layperson” are often fluid, and legitimacy is constantly

negotiated. The PoTSG builds on this insight by inviting participants to step into roles that may differ significantly from their own and simulate what it feels like to be heard — or not — within a stakeholder network.

Moments of Translation as Game Mechanics

Callon (1984) describes four "moments" of translation that shape how actor-networks are built: problematisation, interessement, enrolment, and mobilisation. These concepts are not presented as abstract theory in the PoTSG but are instead embedded into the structure and sequencing of the game.

- **Problematisation:** The game opens with a shared scenario (e.g., agricultural waste and soil degradation), which serves as a common problem space. Participants must interpret this issue from their assigned role's perspective.
- **Interessement:** Players begin negotiating, seeking to stabilize their position and convince others of their relevance or priority.
- **Enrolment:** Roles and responsibilities are clarified as participants build alliances or confront conflict.
- **Mobilisation:** Finally, a collective statement or policy proposal is drafted, giving form to the network's negotiated outcome.

These stages offer players a guided experience of what it takes to align diverse actors, not through top-down planning, but through situated negotiation and performative interaction. The game thus transforms Callon's theory into a lived, reflective experience.

What Makes This Game Different

Role-play simulations and serious games are not new in participatory and learning settings. However, most focus on systems thinking (e.g., system maps), decision-making under constraints (e.g., trade-off games), or strategy development. The PoTSG adds something different: a focus on relational dynamics and negotiation as a process. Furthermore, the game contributes to the expanding use of serious games in living labs and co-creation spaces (Schäpke et al., 2018; Leminen, 2015), adding a performative, relational lens to typically technocratic or process-driven approaches. Rather than simulating the outcomes of aligned systems, it simulates the messy path of getting there. The game does not prescribe correct decisions. Instead, it invites participants to inhabit positionality: What does it feel like to speak from a marginal role? What compromises are possible? What assumptions are challenged? These affective and performative elements are difficult to achieve through traditional facilitation.

Moreover, the explicit use of Callon’s Obligatory Passage Point (OPP) concept allows the group to collectively define a “point of alignment” that holds the network together, surfacing not only what agreements are made but how they are made, by whom, and at what cost. In this sense, the PoTSG is not only a facilitation tool but a methodological intervention. It provides Living Lab practitioners with a way to:

- Build empathy across actor roles.
- Explore how legitimacy and power circulate in real-world settings.
- Reflect on their own positioning in co-creation processes.

Used as a training tool, it can help researchers and practitioners become more attuned to the social labour of collaboration. Used as a research method, it can surface patterns of inclusion, conflict, and alliance formation that often remain hidden in conventional data.

Method and Data

Participants

This paper draws on observational data collected during the initial pilot of the Process of Translation Serious Game, conducted at the ESNI 2024 conference in Brussels. The session involved 18 participants, including researchers, policymakers, and practitioners from across the quadruple helix. The authors served as both facilitators and participant-observers, guiding the game’s structure while documenting the interactions that unfolded.

Game Description

The serious game “*Building the Common Ground*” was designed to simulate multi-actor negotiation in the context of sustainable agriculture and the circular economy. Grounded in Michel Callon’s theory of translation, the game invites participants to navigate the process of aligning diverse interests through the identification and negotiation of a shared *matter of concern*.

The game begins with each participant (or team) receiving a role card (see figure 1 for a mock of the cards shared and Table 1 for the full text as presented in the cards shared), which outlines the goals, constraints, resources, and perspectives of a particular actor in the agricultural ecosystem. These roles span the quadruple helix of stakeholders, academia, industry, government, and civil society, and include farmers, researchers, policymakers, producers, advisors, local authorities, and environmental advocates.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Participants are asked to fully inhabit their assigned roles, adopting the associated priorities and viewpoints throughout the session.

The session opens with the introduction of a scenario that serves as a problematisation prompt: a recent surge in agricultural waste has led to significant soil degradation and water pollution in the region. The actors, brought together as a network, are tasked with formulating a shared and actionable response that benefits all stakeholders while promoting circular economy principles. A facilitator, either one of the participants or an external guide, moderates the session. The facilitator ensures adherence to time limits, supports equitable participation, and steers the conversation toward uncovering shared interests and potential synergies.

Table 1. Text used on identity role cards used in the game.

Category	Fictional Name	Role Description (shared with players)
Agricultural Advisor	Brian O'Sullivan	"Hello, my name is Brian O'Sullivan, and I'm an agricultural advisor with the Department of Agriculture. I work closely with farmers across County Tipperary, helping them adopt more sustainable practices while staying productive and profitable. I'm really excited about the living lab because it provides a space where we can test out new ideas and help farmers transition to circular economy models in a practical, hands-on way."
SME	Tom Fitzgerald	"Hi, I'm Tom Fitzgerald, and I run EcoEnergy Solutions, a company based in County Cork that specializes in processing agricultural and food waste into biofuel and organic fertilisers. We work with local farms and food producers to turn their waste into valuable resources, helping to reduce landfill use and lower carbon emissions. I'm excited to join this living lab to explore how circular economy practices can further enhance the sustainability of our operations and benefit the local farming community."
Start up	Sarah Brennan	"Hi, I'm Sarah Brennan, founder of NutriCycle Innovations, a startup based in Dublin. We develop high-quality food supplements using nutrients extracted from agricultural bio-waste, like vegetable peels and spent grain from breweries. By repurposing these by-products, we create sustainable, nutrient-rich supplements for health-conscious consumers. I'm excited to join this living lab to explore how we can collaborate with farmers and producers to turn waste into valuable products that benefit both the environment and the market."
Policy Advisor	Siobhán Murphy	"Hi, my name is Siobhán Murphy, and I'm a policy advisor with the Irish Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine. My work focuses on developing policies that support sustainable farming and rural development. I'm excited to be part of this living lab because it provides a real-world testing ground for new policies that promote circular economy practices and help farmers transition to greener methods."
Local Authority staff	John Keane	"Hello, I'm John Keane, and I work for Limerick City and County Council as a rural development officer. My job is to ensure that local communities are involved in sustainable initiatives that enhance both the economy and the environment. I'm particularly interested in how we can support farmers and

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

		producers in adopting circular economy practices that will benefit our community in the long term."
Environmental NGO Representative	Claire O'Donnell	"Hi, I'm Claire, and I work with An Taisce, an Irish environmental NGO that focuses on sustainability and environmental protection. Our goal is to support sustainable agricultural practices that preserve biodiversity, reduce waste, and enhance the resilience of ecosystems. In this living lab, I'll be advocating for practices that not only improve efficiency but also help restore and protect our natural environment."
Community Cooperative Representative	Eoin O'Reilly	"Hi, I'm Eoin, and I'm a member of the Moy Valley Community Cooperative, a local group in County Mayo that supports small-scale farmers and producers through cooperative buying, marketing, and resource-sharing initiatives. Our goal is to help local farmers access sustainable markets and improve livelihoods. I'm excited to join this living lab to ensure that the solutions developed also work for smallholders and cooperatives like ours."
Farmer	Jack O'Connor	"Hi, my name is Jack, and I'm a farmer from County Waterford, Ireland. I manage a farm of 120 acres where I primarily grow barley and oats, but I also rear a small herd of dairy cows. Sustainability is important to me, and I've been experimenting with crop rotation and reducing chemical inputs to make my farm more environmentally friendly. I'm excited to be part of this living lab to explore how circular economy practices can enhance what we're already doing."
Researcher	Dr. Aoife Kelly	"Hi, I'm Dr. Aoife Kelly, and I'm a researcher at Teagasc, specialising in agricultural sustainability and circular economy models. My work focuses on finding innovative ways to reduce waste in farming and develop more efficient uses of resources like water and energy. I'm really looking forward to collaborating with farmers and other stakeholders in the living lab to bring evidence-based solutions that can transform the sector toward greater sustainability."
Researcher	Dr. Niamh Gallagher	"Hi, I'm Dr. Niamh Gallagher, a biologist at the University of Limerick specialising in soil health and ecosystem services. My research focuses on improving soil fertility, promoting biodiversity, and developing regenerative agricultural practices that enhance soil resilience. I'm eager to contribute to this living lab by exploring how soil health can be optimised in circular economy models, benefiting both farmers and the environment."

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Figure 1. Illustration of the cards shared with participants

The gameplay unfolds over five structured phases:

- **Introductions and Goal Sharing (15 minutes):** Participants introduce their roles, articulate their goals, and highlight the constraints and opportunities relevant to their actor. This opening round surfaces the diversity of perspectives and establishes the groundwork for identifying overlaps and tensions. Participants also identify their position within the quadruple helix by marking their stakeholder category on a shared visual display.
- **Debate and Negotiation (20 minutes):** Building on their initial statements, participants propose solutions to the shared problem. They are encouraged to challenge each other’s ideas constructively while actively seeking areas of common ground. This phase emphasises the multiplicity of possible framings and potential pathways, mirroring real-world tensions in multi-stakeholder collaboration.
- **Identifying Synergies and Core Agreements (20 minutes):** The group turns its attention to identifying key principles or proposals that can gain broad support. Negotiation deepens as participants modify their initial positions, aiming to build consensus. The emphasis is on finding “win-win” outcomes—solutions where the interests of one actor can be aligned with, or leveraged to support, those of others.
- **Drafting a Common Matter of Concern (15 minutes):** Participants collaboratively draft a collective statement or action plan that reflects their negotiated agreement. This output, shaped through compromise and dialogue, serves as a performative

expression of the group's alignment and shared intent. It is typically framed as a policy statement, commitment, or coordinated intervention.

- **Final Reflection (10 minutes):** The session concludes with a reflection round in which participants step back from their roles to consider the dynamics of the process. Guiding questions prompt them to reflect on the compromises made, how their understanding of the issue evolved, and how the shared outcome reflects the broader principles of sustainability and circularity. This phase also surfaces meta-insights about participation, inclusion, and actor configuration, specifically, the importance of recognising who was (or wasn't) "in the room."

Together, these phases facilitate an experiential learning process in which players practice systems thinking, stakeholder alignment, and collaborative problem-solving. More importantly, the game provides a microcosm of the translation process central to socio-technical change, demonstrating how coordination and consensus emerge not from top-down planning but through situated negotiation and relational engagement.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection focused on real-time observation of participants' engagement, with particular attention to three key areas. 1. Role enactment, including how participants interpreted and performed their assigned stakeholder roles, including the use of language, gestures, and framing of interests. 2. Nature of dialogue, including the character of interactions during negotiation phases, including moments of agreement, disagreement, persuasion, and compromise. 3. Emergent themes and dynamics, including patterns in how participants navigated conflicts, built alliances, or shifted positions over the course of the game.

Field notes were recorded independently by both authors and synthesised post-session to identify recurring themes and notable moments. The observational focus allowed us to capture the performative and relational aspects of role-play, offering insights into how participants embodied stakeholder positions and engaged with the game's negotiation challenges.

Limitations

This paper presents the findings from an initial pilot implementation of the Process of Translation Serious Game (PoTSG), drawing primarily on observational data gathered during its delivery at the ESNI 2024 conference. While this approach offers valuable

insight into participant engagement, role enactment, and the dynamics of multi-actor negotiation, it has important limitations.

Most notably, we did not collect post-session interview or survey data from participants. As a result, our analysis is limited to facilitator field notes and real-time observations, without the benefit of participants' direct reflections on their experiences, learning outcomes, or suggestions for improvement. While several moments of insight and affective engagement were clearly observable during the session, we recognise that relying solely on observation constrains our ability to interpret participants' internal responses or trace longer-term impacts.

This limitation reflects the exploratory and developmental nature of the current study. The session was designed as a proof-of-concept pilot, focused on testing the game's structure, flow, and facilitation model in a live setting. Based on the promising results from this initial iteration, we are planning further implementations in both academic and applied Living Lab contexts. These future iterations will incorporate additional data collection, including semi-structured interviews, participant feedback surveys, and potentially pre- and post-session reflections. This will enable a deeper understanding of the game's learning impact, its potential for stakeholder training, and the ways in which it may need to be adapted for different audiences or contexts.

In sum, while the current study demonstrates the feasibility and relevance of PoTSG as a serious game for stakeholder alignment, further empirical research is needed to evaluate its effectiveness more comprehensively and refine its design for broader application.

Results

The initial implementations of the *Theory of Translation Serious Game*, including its delivery at the European Sustainable Nutrition Initiative (ESNI) 2024 conference in Brussels, demonstrated the game's value in enabling participants to explore the complexity of cross-sector collaboration. The structured role-play format provided a safe, performative space for participants to embody stakeholder perspectives from across the quadruple helix, and in doing so, to pre-experience the negotiation, constraint, and alignment processes that characterise real-world living labs.

Participants were assigned role cards representing a diversity of actors including farmers, researchers, policy makers, NGO advocates, producers, and local authority figures. These cards outlined the goals, constraints, and resources of the actor, and participants were encouraged to remain "in role" throughout the process. In practice, this requirement

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

fostered an intensity of engagement that was both surprising and revealing. Several participants were observed to fully occupy the logics and priorities of their assigned roles, including those with which they might ordinarily disagree.

One particularly powerful moment arose when an environmental NGO advocate drew a role card representing a government department position, either from agriculture or the environment. Upon introducing her character, she stated that the central concern from this role's perspective was that "the size of the national herd cannot decrease." She noted that this was a position she had frequently heard in policy discussions and one she had spent much of her professional life contesting. Yet, in taking on the character and articulating this stance out loud, she experienced something unexpected: those around the table, representing a range of other roles, voiced agreement. This moment created a profound and layered insight for the participant. First, she experienced what it felt like to hold a position that others quickly supported, something that in her advocacy work she rarely encounters. Second, she noted the emotional impact of being listened to, and of having one's position accepted as legitimate from the outset. Third, it highlighted the disconnect between her usual role, struggling to convince others of an environmentally focused position and the relative ease of support when occupying a more institutionally embedded stance. For the researchers, this underscored the game's capacity to reveal how legitimacy and consensus are not just matters of content, but of position and power within the stakeholder network.

Figure 2. collage of image of the serious game in action

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Other participants also demonstrated deep engagement with their roles. In two teams in particular, individuals appeared to fully embody the values and logic of the actor they were representing. Those playing industry-aligned roles spoke convincingly about the need for profitability and a clear business case, while those representing community or cooperative actors advocated for equitable access and collective benefit. Observers noted a surprising willingness among participants to argue from perspectives far removed from their own. This willingness not only supported empathetic understanding across sectors but also revealed how role-play can serve as a reflective mirror where participants became aware not just of other positions, but of how these positions are typically received and responded to within a system of action.

Participants reported that the role-play format allowed them to externalise both their own assumptions and those of the roles they inhabited. This process made structural and institutional constraints more visible. For example, a participant playing a local government official acknowledged alignment with environmental concerns but stressed the limitations of funding and policy cycles. This reframed the discussion from one of persuasion to one of support, that is, how might other actors work within or around those constraints to achieve shared objectives? Rather than framing disagreement as a personal or ideological divide, participants began to explore misalignment as a matter of feasibility and interdependence. This shift in orientation was noted by facilitators as a key strength of the game, allowing participants to encounter the performative labour of translation in practice.

The structure of the game was also noted to provide a sense of psychological safety. Participants, including more junior researchers or students, reported that playing a role distinct from their own position enabled them to experiment with articulating views they might otherwise feel hesitant to voice. For some, this meant inhabiting a position of institutional power; for others, it meant defending a marginalised viewpoint with more confidence, knowing that the role gave them permission to do so. This distancing effect allowed individuals to reflect on the dynamics of power, inclusion, and representation in a way that was both affectively and cognitively engaging.

At the same time, several observations raised questions about how the game structure shaped the nature of the interaction. Many teams moved rapidly into solution design, in part due to the way the problem was framed at the start of the session. The scenario was introduced as a clear, pressing issue, that is agricultural waste and soil degradation, which appeared to prompt immediate agreement on the importance of addressing it.

While this clarity helped drive momentum, it may have also truncated opportunities for deeper contestation or exploration of divergent problem framings. Some facilitators reflected that the instruction to hold firmly to one's assigned position may have contributed to a somewhat rigid negotiation process, with fewer moments of compromise than might be expected in real-world settings.

Nonetheless, the collaborative drafting of a shared matter of concern in the later phases of the game revealed how actors were able to move from strongly held positions toward the articulation of a collective commitment. The final policy proposals varied by group, but each reflected a negotiated outcome that balanced ecological, economic, and social concerns. Participants reported a strong sense of satisfaction in having arrived at these shared outcomes, despite initial divergence.

The final reflection phase revealed additional insights. Participants highlighted how the game illuminated the ways in which legitimacy is unevenly distributed across actors, and how this shapes whose ideas gain traction in collaborative settings. Several commented on the importance of being attentive to “who is in the room” and how the absence of certain perspectives can skew the trajectory of co-creation. Others noted how the experience might translate into their own professional contexts, helping them to approach stakeholder engagement with greater empathy and strategic awareness.

Discussion

This study set out to address a persistent challenge within Living Lab practice: how to support meaningful and reflexive stakeholder engagement in contexts marked by competing interests, uneven power dynamics, and epistemic pluralism. As noted in the literature, Living Labs often fall short of their co-creation ambitions due to limited tools for surfacing tensions, building empathy, and navigating alignment across the quadruple helix (Engels et al., 2019; Nguyen & Marques, 2022; Schrevel *et al.*, 2020). In response, we proposed the Theory of Translation Serious Game as an experiential method grounded in Michel Callon's (1986) sociology of translation to simulate and reflect on the processes of problematisation, interessement, enrolment, and mobilisation in a hybrid forum.

The findings from the ESNI 2024 pilot demonstrate that the game created an immersive and psychologically safe space where participants could experiment with stakeholder perspectives and explore negotiation processes that are often implicit or obscured in conventional engagement settings. By requiring participants to embody unfamiliar roles, sometimes in tension with their own values or professional identities, the game revealed

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

how actor positions are both socially constructed and structurally constrained. For instance, when an environmental NGO advocate adopted the voice of a Department of Agriculture official defending herd size, the dissonance of articulating a position they personally oppose became a powerful moment of insight. It highlighted how legitimacy is conferred differently depending on one's institutional role and illustrated the cognitive and affective dynamics of trying to be heard from a marginalised standpoint.

This finding speaks directly to the literature on epistemic ordering in Living Labs. As Haraway (2013) and Callon et al. (2011) argue, hybrid forums demand not only that different knowledges be included but also that actors grapple with how their knowledge claims are received, translated, or silenced. Conventional co-design methods, while valuable, often underplay this power-laden terrain (Schrevel et al., 2020; Mbatha and Musango, 2022). The PoTSG, by contrast, makes such dynamics experientially accessible, offering participants a felt sense of both authority and marginalisation, depending on the role they play.

The game's ability to render visible the constraints shaping action was another key outcome. Participants not only debated preferred solutions but also encountered what it feels like to face institutional or structural limitations, budgetary constraints, policy cycles, or lack of jurisdiction, that restrict what is possible. This echoes Fleury *et al.*'s (2006) argument that translation work in participatory innovation is often mediated by both social and material limits. Rather than viewing disagreement as a matter of personal or ideological divergence, participants began to approach it as a matter of structural feasibility and interdependence. This reorientation aligns with Callon's (1999) assertion that problematisation is not about eliminating difference, but about recognising it as a condition for collaborative action.

Furthermore, the game operationalised Callon's concept of the Obligatory Passage Point (OPP) not as a fixed entity but as something to be discovered, negotiated, and reframed through actor dialogue. Participants moved from individual interests to a collectively drafted matter of concern, often reformulating their original positions in response to others. This performative alignment resonates with the work of Salt *et al.* (2017) and Mallard and Callon (2022), who argue that co-production of knowledge requires tools that make visible the recursive, negotiated, and contingent nature of agreement. As suggested by Clavier et al., (2012) theorising translation practices helps understand how knowledge is produced at the interface between academic and experiential (or lay) knowledge.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Despite these strengths, the pilot also surfaced some limitations. Participants often moved quickly into solution design, in part because the game's opening scenario framed the problem in relatively clear terms. While this helped generate momentum, it may have reduced space for deeper exploration of divergent problem framings, which are often a source of contestation in real-world Living Labs (Minniti & Magaudda, 2025). Additionally, the instruction to hold firmly to one's assigned role sometimes led to more adversarial positioning than is typical in practice. Future iterations of the game might introduce structured prompts or design interventions that encourage role fluidity, reflection on compromise, and the co-construction of actor identities—thereby simulating more iterative forms of enrolment and mobilisation (Callon, 1984; Smith et al., 2010).

The performative and affective dimensions of the game were especially valuable for junior researchers or participants unfamiliar with systems-level negotiation. Participants reported that role-play enabled them to explore alternative power positions, rehearse ways of framing issues, and experiment with modes of engagement they might not otherwise feel entitled to access. This supports Hansen and Fuglsang's (2020) call for engagement methods that can build not just shared visions, but the interpersonal and affective capacities required to sustain collaboration.

Taken together, the findings suggest that serious games like the PoTSG can enrich Living Lab practice in several ways. First, they offer a methodologically grounded means of operationalising the sociology of translation, allowing actors to experience rather than merely learn about the dynamics of stakeholder alignment. Second, they provide a forum for embodied reflexivity, where participants not only simulate roles but also reflect on their reception, voice, and legitimacy within a system. Third, they create conditions for experimentation with alignment strategies, helping participants to understand not only how alignment is achieved, but also how it feels.

In conclusion, the Theory of Translation Serious Game contributes to the Living Lab methodology landscape by filling a critical gap identified in the literature: the need for experiential tools that foreground the relational, negotiated, and political dimensions of stakeholder engagement. As Living Labs are increasingly tasked with supporting transitions to sustainable and regenerative futures, methods that foster empathy, expose systemic constraints, and build capacity for collaborative negotiation will be essential. While not a substitute for real-world engagement, serious play offers a powerful complement to existing co-creation approaches and invites further research into how role-play simulations can support long-term stakeholder learning, trust-building, and systemic change.

Conclusion

This serious game builds on an established literature on role-play and simulation games as tools for participatory learning and stakeholder engagement (Barreteau et al., 2007; Snaphaan et al 2022). While role-play games have long been used in environmental governance, policy development, and organisational learning, the Theory of Translation Serious Game occupies a distinctive niche by embedding Callon's sociology of translation at its theoretical core. Where many role-play games focus on simulating decisions or exploring systems (Kolb & Kolb, 2010; Voinov & Bousquet, 2010), this game foregrounds the relational and performative work of translation, the process by which actors align their interests through negotiation, compromise, and problematisation (Fleury et al., 2006). By explicitly working towards the identification of an OPP, the game makes visible the socio-material labour involved in forming alliances and stabilising networks (Callon, 1986).

In summary, the game provided a compelling means for participants to experience the dynamics of translation, alignment, and negotiation that are central to living lab work. It surfaced the systemic, relational, and emotional dimensions of collaboration, allowing participants to reflect on both the possibilities and the limits of collective action. The depth of role engagement observed, and the emotional resonance of key moments, suggest that serious games like this can play a vital role in preparing stakeholders for the challenges of real-world sustainability transitions.

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Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

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